

SIMILIARITIES BETWEEN I. YUSUPOV'S TRANSLATIONS AND МАКТЫМКУЛИ'S ORIGINAL WORKS

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Annotation: This page presents the creative translation of the works of Turkmen poet Maktymkuli from the 18th century into the Karakalpak language. It is noteworthy that all of the poet's translations are presented in this manner.

Key words: Literary connection, beautiful translation, genius, poet.

One of the most significant forms of literary communication is literary translation. The explanation for this is that an artistic translator is essential to bridging the gap between two countries' literary traditions. As a result, the growth of literary ties in Turkmen-Karakalpak literature is greatly influenced by artistic translators. For instance, Turkmen poets K. Gurbannepevov, A. Mammedov, N. Meredov, and others translated Karakalpak poetry into Turkmen, while I. Yusupov, U. Pirzhanov, A. Utepbergenov, and T. Matmuratov made significant contributions to the translation of Maktymkuli songs into Karakalpak language. The translations of "Turkmannoma" by A. Mammedov, "Kunkhodja, Ajiniyaz, Berdakh" by K. Gurbannepevov, and "Dostluk chemeni" by K. Gurbannepevov, among other poetic works by international authors. The writings of Karakalpak poets like Kunkhoja, Ajiniyaz, and Berdakh were translated into Turkmen.

In Maktymkuli's work "I don't know which Hijran" the poet got involved in the teachings of Sufism, complained about being lost on its difficult path, went through the good and the bad, the pain and the bad, the time, and contrasted the wide world with the narrow world.

Man dunyoni osmondagi oy bildim,
Issi-issiq asilishdim, song bildim,
Imdi aning barin-yogun teng bildim,
Sud qaysidir, ziyon qaysi, bilmadim.
Magtımqulı, yoling uningi, ardi bor,
Cheker yukun, xer kishining merdi bor,
Yuragda pınxan ıshqıng dardi bor,
Dart kaysıdır, darman kaysı, bilmadim.

I. Yusupov translated the word "I don't know" as his theme:

Yoqdi jahon dedim, avval keng bildim,
Yolğanshı va tor ekanini song bildim,

Endi uning barin, yogin teng bildim,
Foyda qaysi, ziyon qaysi, bilmadim.
Maqtimquli, yo'lning oldi -orti bor,
Yuk ko'tarsa, har kishining mardi bor,
Qalbimning pitmas ishq dardi bor,
Dardlarimi darmon qaysi, bilmadim.

In this translation, the method of swearing is preserved as in the original. The reason is that the translator has kept the appearance of the song in this form, taking into account that the swearing method is widely used to enhance the expressiveness of the reflected thought in the work. This phenomenon determines the skill of the interpreter. However, it seems that the poet made a slight mistake in correctly explaining the content of the poem. For example, in the previous paragraph, Maktymkuli said, "I saw the world as the moon in the sky, I hung hot and cold, then I knew" and equated his Sufi path with the "moon in the sky" who thought that it was easy to get out, and then I learned that his path is difficult. "I said I liked the world, first I knew it was wide, then I realized that it was false and narrow" - it is said about this world. Here the difference is noticeable in the content.

In the original, it is quoted as "There is a secret love pain in my heart" - "There is a secret love pain in my heart." Love in Maktymkuli is a dangerous love - it is a love that happened to Yazdon on his accidental way. In some translations, the word "pitpes" does not mean the word "secret". Here, the content of Maktymkuly's song is not corrected. In the translation

I. Yusupov translated it into the Karakalpak language by I. Yusupov, based on the Sufi doctrine of "Jon Ichida" by Maktimkuli. First of all, the striking style of the mane, the beautiful details, the beautiful methods of depiction immediately bring to mind the style of Maktymkuli. In order to understand Maktymkuli's song "Inside the Soul", it is necessary to be familiar with the teachings of Sufi. However, I. Yusupov took into account these circumstances and stopped translating the song. For example:

Fikr qildim bosimda,
Aqlsiz jon ichida.
Jon va mablag' xiromasında
Yet, singdir, qon ichida.
Bo'lsa haqli'q, grafaat,
Dunyoning mulki abat,
Galma-galpıllıqta, odamzod,

Qolding orzu ichida.

Nafsing aytadigan : «yutsam» dar,
«Qarmat hid etsam» dar,
«Ichsam, esam, yotsam - dar -
Yaxna hayvon ichida».

In original:

Fikr kıldım yer -gógi

Biakıl Jon ichida.

Ko'rdúm, Jon xem «Allalik! » diyr,
Yet, singdir, gan ichida.

Gider yoluń bilmasang,

Dogrı yola gelmasang,

Xakı yoda zovursang,

Galding arman ichida.

Nimabsing haydar : «Josh bo'lsam,
Gókjeklere duchh bo'lsam,
Iysem-ichsem, xush bo'lsam,
Yatsam mardumvan ichida».

This song of Maktymkuli consists of 34 clauses. I. Yusupov translated 26 paragraphs of this poem. We think that it is reasonable to mention one thing here. When I. Yusupov translated song, he took the meaning of words not only in their place, but in a general way.

The quality of Yusupov's translations varies. Certain hymns have straightforward translations that omit important details. K. Tarkibbaev stated that "Maktymkuli's poetic skill has sometimes become shallow in translations," citing the translation of "Turkmen" by Maktymkuli as an illustration. We are hesitant to voice our thoughts regarding the poet's translations, nevertheless. The rationale is that we are pleased with the ratio of high-quality translations to low-quality translations based on research. Because of this, I. Yusupov's translation of Maktymkuli's artistic works, which are split into enigmatic lines, demonstrates the poet's talent. The reason for this is that no translator can be bitter about Maktymkuli's poetry. It appears to be a well-kept secret. This enigmatic secret was translated into Karakalpak by I. Yusupov.

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